

Resort Operation Management Practices in a Beach Municipality of Sariaya, Quezon Philippines

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Abstract:- According to Department of Tourism (DOT) Secretary B. R. Puyat (2019), the Philippine tourism is now a PHP2.2-trillion national industries that generates 12.7 percent of the country's GDP and employs about 5.4 million people in passenger transport, accommodations, and food and beverages, among others. Thus, this study focus on the resort operation management practices in a beach municipality of Sariaya, Quezon Philippine 4322. This study used a descriptive-quantitative research design and a self-made questionnaire is utilized as the main tool to gather the data. A paired t-test is also used to see the significant difference of the responses of the employees and guest. The respondents of this study are resort owners, employees and guest. Study reveals that resort operation in beach municipality are well manage, this is supported by the result of the paired t-test conducted to see the significant difference between the responses of the respondents.

Keywords:- beach, resort, management, tourism, practices.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is perhaps the world's fastest expanding business, and it is viewed as a means of economic development, particularly in underdeveloped countries and areas. Tourism is one of the most critical sectors in the Philippines. According to the Department of Tourism (2016), tourism earnings hit \$6 billion in 2016, up from \$5 billion the previous year. Tourism brought much strain in terms of its effects on natural, cultural, and social surroundings in the 1970s (UNEP & UNWTO, 2005). This pressure resulted in some unexpected alterations in the perception of tourism. Continuous development principles and their implementation are the most influencing policy in the hospitality industry over the years, with research studies have focused on the local levels instead of the company's business micro-level (Dwyer, 2011).

The idea of sustainable tourism has grown in importance, becoming more prominent on national and international agendas. The United Nations General Assembly has passed multiple resolutions recognizing tourism's role as a tool for development, poverty eradication, and environmental protection, culminating in the UN declaring 2017 the International Year of Sustainable Tourism for Development (IY2017). Tourism is especially pertinent in light of the approval of the United Nations 2030 Development Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the international community (UNWTO, 2017).

This paper examined the resort operation management practices to have a sustainable tourism industry in the municipality of Sariaya, Quezon Philippines. The local government had seen the importance of development and changes in the past years. In the economic development, the privatization and observable business indicators, such as major resort investment help in the development. With these investments, tourism was developed more and the efficiency of resort management had seen advancement (Assaf&KneževićCvelbar, 2010) as experienced in the region 4a area. Even in the noticeable growth and development of the tourism industry, there are still more to look and focus to continuously improved this sector.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The purpose of this research was to describe the resort operation management in a beach municipality. Specifically, it sought to answer the following; 1. What is the profile of the resorts in Sariaya, Quezon, 2. The operation being practiced by resorts in a beach municipality, 3. Is there a significant difference between the responses made by the resort staff and guest on the resort management practices?

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive-quantitative research design. Descriptive research provides a relatively complete picture of what is occurring at a given time and at the same time allows the development of questions for further study (Stangor, 2011). Descriptive research is used in this study because it aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. It can answer what, when, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions (McCombes, 2019). This study was conducted to determine the resort operation management practices in a beach municipality.

The research was conducted in different resorts which were initially choose, resorts operating in Sariaya, Quezon Philippines 4322, the owner/manager as respondents, to form one part of the pool of respondents to answer the survey questionnaire.

The respondents of this study were the 200 respondents, 10 resort employees and 10 resort guests for each of the 10 resorts. Using a simple random sampling method, the respondent was chosen. The researcher utilized a self-made questionnaire with close-ended questions as the main tool to gather data. According to McLeod (2018), a questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions to gather information from respondents. It can be thought of as a kind of written interview. They can be

carried out face to face, by telephone, computer or post, in this study the research visited the resorts face to face to get their responses.

The responses received from the respondents were organized, classified, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using frequency distribution, and percentage. All Computations were done using Microsoft Excel. The following numerical and adjectival values were used:

Scale of Values	Scale of Range	Verbal interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the data gather concerning the resorts operation management in a beach municipality of Sariaya, Quezon Philippines 4322.

A. Part I. Profile of the Resort’s Owners

No.	Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Ownership			
1.	Sole Proprietorship	8	80%
2.	Corporation	2	20%
	Total	10	100%
Land Size			
1.	1000 – 3000sqms	2	20%
2.	3001 – 5000sqms	3	30%
3.	5001 – 7000sqms	4	40%
4.	9,000sqms and above	1	10%
	Total	10	100%
Length of Resort Business Operation			
1.	10 years and below	2	20%
2.	11 years and above	8	80%
	Total	10	100%
Number of Employees			
1.	10 – 30 staffs	6	60%
2.	31 – 50 staffs	2	20%
3.	51 staffs and above	2	20%
	Total	10	100%
Department of Tourism (DOT) Accreditation			
1.	Accredited	2	20%
2.	Not Accredited	2	20%
3.	On-going application	6	60%
	Total	10	100%
Facilities and Amenities (Multiple answers are allowed)			
1.	Business areas	6	8.45%
2.	Arrival and departure Areas	10	14.08%
3.	Public Areas	10	14.08%
4.	Bedrooms	10	14.08%
5.	Bathrooms	10	14.08%
6.	Food and Beverage Stores	8	11.26%
7.	Recreations and Sports Area	8	11.26%
8.	Emergency and Clinic Service Area	9	12.67%
	Total	71	100%

Table 1: Profile of the Resort’s Owners

Table 1 above shows the data of the demographic profile of the resorts in the beach municipality. Majority or 80% of the resorts are sole proprietorship. This means that resorts owners still considers the benefits a sole

proprietorship form of the business. According to Permwanichagun et. Al, (2014) such a business classification is popular because it is easy to set up and carries a low cost for a first investment. A sole proprietor

only registers his or her business name for local licenses; then, after that, the business is ready to be run. As to land size, 1 or 10% only has a 9001sq.ms and above land size showing that only one resort has a big space area, 4 or 40% have 5001 – 7000 sq.ms, which is a medium or average land size and 5 or 50% have 5000sq.ms and below which is a small or common land size of resorts. Land size is one of the important consideration is putting up a resort, maximizing space and ensuring a convenient set up is one of the reasons for guest to visit a resort. Also, considering the majority of the resorts are a sole proprietorship business signify that the owners have limited source of fund to buy or lease a larger land size. The length of the business operation reveals that majority or 80% of the resorts are operating 11 years and above, thus, resorts business in the beach municipality is a sustainable business, moreover, one of the most chosen destinations of the local and foreign tourist are the beach and resorts, especially if they have a beautiful spot.

As to the number of employees, majority or 60% of the resorts have 10 – 30 staffs and the rest have 31 and above staff. Staffing is one of the major function in management, staffing is usually based on the capacity of the business operation. Having more staff can be expensive but it can ensure more customer satisfaction since more staff is available to assist the guests. Wroblewski (2020) said that, staffing isn't just about finding any person to fill it a job; the purpose of staffing should be about finding the ideal person for a job.

B. Part II. The Operation Being Practiced by Resorts in A Beach Municipality

Accreditation adds appeal to a business, the data above reveals that only 2 or 20% of the resorts operating in beach municipality are accredited, 2 or 20% are not accredited and 60% are currently applying for the DOT accreditation. It reveals that only 20% of the resorts have fully comply with the minimum standards in the operation of the establishment which shall ensure the safety, comfort, and convenience of the tourists. Tourism stakeholders should guarantee that they deliver quality service and being accredited will help the business in the long run. Lastly, the facilities and amenities, data reveals that out of the 8 indicators no. 2,3,4,5, have the highest percentage of 14.08, which indicates that “most” if not all of them have the following mentioned above facilities and amenities, this is followed by Medical and Clinic Services with 12.67%, which means “most” if not all of have available medical and clinic service. First aid service is one of the important facilities an establishment should have because it will ensure the safety and security of all the stakeholders of the business.

Furthermore, findings signify that most of the resorts operating in the municipality are owned and operated by one person, it is well staff, they considered the DOT accreditation which is an evidence of the safety minimum standard operation of an establishment. They also have almost the same facilities and amenities which shows presence of competitions to have a quality and satisfying customer experience.

No.	Indicators	Employee’s Response	Guest’s Response	Total Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Resort name clearly visible from the street and visible at night time.	4.74	4.6	4.70	Strongly Agree
	Has unique exterior and visual appeal	4.74	4.66	4.70	Strongly Agree
	Quality materials are used in the construction of the building.	4.86	4.76	4.81	Strongly Agree
	Very good maintenance of paintwork and exterior panels checked for rust, flake, rot, etc.	4.78	4.72	4.75	Strongly Agree
	Planned architectural features are evident or theme of the resort fit the physical condition.	4.80	4.74	4.77	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean		4.78	4.71	4.75	Strongly Agree

Table 2: Resort Operation in terms of Condition and Appearance of Resort Buildings

Table 2 shows that both employees and guest both “strongly Agree” that the conditions and appearance of the resorts are in good conditions. Statement no. 3 “Quality materials are used in the construction of the building.” has the highest total weighted mean of 4.81 with verbal interpretation “Strongly Agree”. This signifies that the resorts are prioritizing the building quality of their establishments. However, statement no. 1” Resort name clearly visible from the street and visible at night time.” And statement no. 2 “has unique exterior and visual appeal” are both have the lowest total mean of 4.70 with verbal interpretation “Strongly Agree”. Although the verbal interpretation for statement no.1 and 2 are “strongly agree”

it can be interpreted that not only the building quality but also the appearance should be considered by the resorts owners.

The exterior and visual appearance is one of the consideration of the guest and tourist to visit a places. This is because most of them wants to take photos and pictures of this place as a remembrance. It has been argued as well in literature on tourism that satisfaction can be the result of the value perceived by the tourist in the place (Mariano, 2017). Thus, we can conclude that the condition and appearance of the resort’s in a beach municipality are still appealing to the guest and employees.

No.	Indicators	Employee's Response	Guest's Response	Total Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	No potholes and obstruction in the arrival and departure areas.	4.70	4.68	4.69	Strongly Agree
	Driveway entrance is clearly visible and properly marked and visible at night time	4.80	4.78	4.79	Strongly Agree
	Clear designated parking area is provided for guest or enough space is provided for guest parking.	4.78	4.72	4.75	Strongly Agree
	Docking area is separated from parking area of guests.	4.54	4.58	4.56	Strongly Agree
	Valet parking is an option open for guests.	4.24	4.46	4.35	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean		4.61	4.64	4.63	Strongly Agree

Table 3: Resort Operation in terms of Resort's Arrival and Departure Area

Table 3. reveals the data for the Arrival and Departure areas of the resorts. Statement no. 2 "Driveway entrance is clearly visible and properly marked and visible at night time" has the highest total weighted mean of 4.79 with verbal interpretation "Strongly Agree". Both employees and guest "Strongly Agree" that the driveway for the guest and tourist are properly marked and visible even at night. Visibility of the drive is important since safety and security of the guest and tourist should be the number 1 priority of the business. Data also shows that statement no. 5 "Valet parking is an option open for guests." With a total weighted

mean of 4.35 and a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree".

Overall, the result shows that all resorts have an assigned driveway for the guest which is set to be the entrance and exit. The Department of Tourism (DOT), have a policy to have a designated parking area for the guests and employees of the resort, this policy was religiously followed and complied by all resorts in the municipality. This parking area for the guests are free of charges

No.	Indicators	Employee's Response	Guest's Response	Total Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Good transport service is available for guest.	4.65	4.33	4.49	Strongly Agree
	Ground transport is in good condition.	4.60	4.56	4.58	Strongly Agree
	No delays made in transporting resorts raw materials, foods, goods, and supplies.	4.56	4.59	4.58	Strongly Agree
	Saving fuel/gas is being observed.	4.64	4.62	4.63	Strongly Agree
	Visibility of public transport service and activity are observable.	4.52	4.44	4.48	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean		4.59	4.51	4.55	Strongly Agree

Table 4: Resort Operation in terms of Transport Service

Table 4. shows the data for the transport service of the resort operation. The data shows that the average weighted mean of the majority if not all "strongly agree" that resorts in beach municipality have a good transport service that can assist and help guests and employees going in and out of the establishment. Going in to the details shows that, statement no. 4 "Saving fuel/gas is being observed" has the highest

total weighted mean of 4.63 with verbal interpretation "strongly agree" this means that resorts are concerned with the transport gas expense on both guests and employees.

Moreover, good transport service and visibility of public transport are in place to improved the service of the resort.

No.	Indicators	Employee's Response	Guest's Response	Total Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Professional security guard in place 24/7 at main entry point.	4.82	4.70	4.76	Strongly Agree
	Staffs are provided by uniforms and name tags.	4.74	4.66	4.70	Strongly Agree
	CCTVs are place strategically.	4.72	4.52	4.62	Strongly Agree
	Trained first aid and life guard staff are available.	4.74	4.54	4.64	Strongly Agree

Well lighted public areas like lobby, bars, swimming pool, and parking areas.	4.70	4.78	4.74	Strongly Agree
Fire alarms and fire extinguishers are appropriately placed	4.66	4.52	4.59	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.73	4.62	4.68	Strongly Agree

Table 5: Resort Operation in terms of Resort’s Safety and Security

Table 5 above shows the data of resort’s safety and security. Safety and security plays an important role in the hospitality industry under tourism (De Castro, 2018). The data above revealed the average weighted mean for the safety and security of resorts is 4.68 with verbal interpretation “Strongly Agree”. This data revealed that safety and security is another priority of the beach resorts. Safety and security is also one of the consideration for a tourist and guest to visit a place.

Detailing the data above, the statement no. 1 “Professional security guard are in place 24/7 at main entry point” has the highest weighted mean of 4.76 with verbal

interpretation “strongly agree”. This can signify that in terms of safety and security guard on point entry is the number indication that it is a priority of the establishment. Statement no. 6 Fire alarms and fire extinguisher are appropriately placed has the lowest total weighted mean of 4.59 with verbal interpretation “strongly agree”, although respondents “strongly agree” that fire alarms and extinguisher are in place it is still noticeable that in safety and security of the guests and employees alarms and fire extinguisher, most establishment are providing this just to get a permit.

No.	Indicators	Employee’s Response	Guest’s Response	Total Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	Reception Service open 24/7.	4.70	4.50	4.60	Strongly Agree
	Online Booking and early reservation are available.	4.50	4.52	4.51	Strongly Agree
	Professional appearance of all reception staff is observed.	4.62	4.64	4.63	Strongly Agree
	Reception lobby fits the size of daily resort operation.	4.70	4.72	4.71	Strongly Agree
	Express Check –in and check-out registration process with no wait time.	4.62	4.48	4.55	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean		4.63	4.57	4.60	Strongly Agree

Table 6: Resort Operation in terms of Resort’s Receptions

Table 6. shows the reception service of the resort in a beach municipality. The average weighted mean is 4.60 with verbal interpretation “strongly Agree”, this data shows that majority of the guests and employees strongly agree that there is good reception service in resorts in a beach municipality.

Have a good reception service encourages more guest to visit the resort, since good customer relation has a factor in building customer loyalty. Thus, this resorts are maintaining and continuously developing their resort operation in terms of receptions.

C. Part III. Is There a Significant Difference Between the Responses Made by the Resort Staff and Guest On the Resort Operation Management Practices?

No.	Resort Operation	Computed T-Value	Critical T. Value	Decisions	Impression at 0.05 level of Significance
	Building	5.013	2.776	Accept H _i	Significant
	Arrival and Departure Areas	-0.645	2.776	Accept H _o	Not Significant
	Transport Services	1.407	2.776	Accept H _o	Not Significant
	Safety and Security	3.222	2.776	Accept H _i	Significant
	Reception Areas	1.179	2.776	Accept H _o	Not Significant

Table 7: Paired t-test for Two Samples: Employees versus Guests on *Best Practices in Resort Operation*

Table 7 shows the result of the paired t-test to see the significant difference of the responses of the guest and employees. It can be seen from the data above that out of 5 indicators, no. 2.3. and 5 are not significant, therefore employees and guest have the same perspectives in term of the resort operation in a beach municipality. However, in

can be seen from the data that indicator 1 and 4 have a significant difference, it means that in term of building and the safety and security, employees and guest have a significant difference in perspective.

Therefore, it may conclude that majority of the response of the respondents both the guest and employees, proves to be true and correct since it has a little of no difference.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the data above, a conclusion is derived. It can be concluded that most of the resorts in the beach municipality are owned and operated by a single person or family, since they are using a sole proprietorship form of the business. Majority of the resort are still processing their application for the accreditation of the DOT. In terms of the resort operation management, both employees and guest strongly agrees that it is properly manage. There is a little or no difference on the responses of the employees and guest based on the paired t-test result presented above.

The research strongly suggests to all the owners of the resorts to focus on the transport service to improve number of guest and tourist visiting their resorts. The safety and security should be maintained and strengthen by the resort's owners especially the reliability of the fire alarms and visibility of the fire extinguishers. Lastly, it is important to prioritize the DOT accreditation since it will be the only strong evidence of the compliance to the minimum standard operation of a beach resort.

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